

Hemicyanines: Part I

J. C. Banerjee, K. D. Banerjee, N. P. Bhattacharya and S. N. Sanyal

"A number of hemicyanine dyes have been prepared, and their sensitisation, absorption and other properties studied."

Since the observation by Mills and Pope¹ that 2-*p*-dimethylaminostyrylpyridine methiodide (a hemicyanine²) was a powerful photographic sensitiser covering the green range of the spectrum, a considerable amount of work has been done by way of preparing diverse styryl dyes with suitable variations³. Thus (i) different heterocyclic quaternary salts, substituted and unsubstituted, each possessing a reactive group, have been condensed with *p*-dimethyl and *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehydes for the preparation of these dyes, (ii) different alkyl halides have been used to quaternise the heterocyclic bases in the dye condensations. Other variations comprise the synthesis of the butadienyl analogues of the styryl cyanines by the condensation of *p*-dimethylaminocinnamic aldehyde with hetero salts and the synthesis of dyes having substituents in the methylenic chains of both the classical styryl cyanines and the butadienyl cyanines.

The above syntheses follow the general scheme:

R, R₁ = Alkyl

n = 0 (in styryl cyanines), 1 (in butadienyl cyanines)

X = I (usually)

1. W. H. Mills and W. J. Pope, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121.

2. Ref. 3, p. 447.

3. For an excellent review on cyanine dyes see "The Cyanine Dyes and Related Compounds" by F. M. Hamer, Interscience Publishers, 1964.

The present investigations were undertaken to study systematically the absorption and sensitisation of some types of hemicyanines, obtainable by varying the carbonyl component of the reactants used in the preparation of these dyes. The types of hemicyanines thus obtained, are described below.

Naphthylidene hemicyanines: Three new dyes (II a, b, c) of this type have been prepared by the condensation of 1-diethylamino-4-naphthaldehyde with 2-methyl-6-chlorobenzthiazole methiodide, 2-methyl-6-bromoquinoline methiodide and 2:4-dimethylthiazole methiodide respectively.

- II(a) Hetero ring = 2-methyl-6-chlorobenzthiazole methiodide
 (b) Hetero ring = 2-methyl-6-bromoquinoline methiodide
 (c) Hetero ring = 2:4-dimethylthiazole methiodide.

These dyes, as will be seen, possess an additional aromatic ring condensed with the original benzene of the classical styryl cyanines derived from *p*-dialkylaminobenzaldehydes. It will be seen that one of the resonance extremes (JB) involves a *p*-quinonoid structure. The fusion of an additional aromatic system to the *p*-quinonoid, in these new dyes, would tend to stabilise the resonance forms of type (JB). The effect would be expected to be reflected on the absorption and sensitisation of these dyes.

The required naphthaldehyde was obtained by formylating diethyl- α -naphthylamine with hexamine and formic acid. The orientation of the substituents in the aldehyde, was determined by oxidation with permanganate when phthalic acid was obtained which confirmed the homoannular character of the substituents. Further, dichromate oxidation of the aldehyde afforded α -naphthaquinone, showing the para orientation of the substituents.

Butadienyl hemicyanines: *p*-Dimethylaminocinnamic aldehyde has been condensed with 2:4-dimethylbenzthiazole methiodide to yield dye IIIb and with 2:4-dimethylthiazole methiodide to yield dye IIIa,

- III(a) Hetero ring = 2:4-dimethylthiazole methiodide.
 III(b) Hetero ring = 2:4-dimethylbenzthiazole methiodide.

As the increase in the length of the conjugated chain in cyanines is known generally to shift the absorption maxima of the dyes to longer wavelengths, it was thought of interest to examine if the same would also be true in the case of hemicyanines. Since the absorption data of a very large number of styryl cyanines are available in the literature, synthesis of analogous butadienyl compounds would be necessary for comparison.

β -Methylstyrylcyanines: The substitution of a methyl group (as also of some others) at α -carbon atom of the methylenic chain of styryl cyanines, has been reported to cause a hypsochromic shift in the absorption maxima in the substituted, as compared to the unsubstituted dyes⁴. We now report the preparation of dye (IV) obtained by the condensation of *p*-dimethylaminoacetophenone with 2:5-dimethylbenzthiazole methiodide.

IV : Hetero ring = 2:5-dimethylbenzthiazole methiodide.

It would be interesting to compare the α -methyl dyes with the β -methyl dyes considering the fact that electron drifts due to hyperconjugative effect of the substituted methyl group may be opposite in the two cases.

β -Methylbutadienyl cyanines: This class of dyes incorporate the features of the dyes of types (III) and (IV). For the present, one dye (V) of this class obtained by condensing *p*-dimethylaminostyryl methyl ketone with 2:6-dimethylbenzthiazole methiodide is being reported.

V : Heteroring = 2 : 6-dimethylbenzthiazole methiodide.

The sensitisation spectra of the dyes are given in Fig. 1; the sensitisation of an un-bathed plate being appended for reference. In table I the absorption and sensitisation figures of the dyes are given along with those of the corresponding styryl dyes, wherever the latter have been available.

It is not, at this stage, possible to generalise the effect of the structural variations on absorption and sensitisation, but from the data now presented, marked bathochromic

shifts both in absorption and sensitisation of the new dyes, are clearly noticeable. Results of further investigation, now in progress, will be communicated shortly.

TABLE 1

Dye	Extra-sensitisation(m μ)		Absorption max. (m μ)	Reference
	Extends upto	Max.		
IIa	700	650	528	
Styryl	656	550	510	Doja & Banerjee, <i>This Journal</i> , 1951, 28 , 7.
IIb	700	590,650	582	Sahay, Sinha & Banerjee, <i>This Journal</i> , 1966, 43 , 255.
Styryl	650	600	560	
IIc	650	590	446	
Styryl	600	540	480	Doja & Banerjee, <i>This Journal</i> , 1946, 23 , 217.
IIIa	720	600	500	
Styryl	595	550	—	Smith, J. L. B, <i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1923, 123 , 2288.
IIIb	760	580,680	526	
Styryl	—	—	—	
IV	680	570	546	
Styryl	670	570	—	Smith, J. L. B, <i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1923, 123 , 2292.
V	740	640	518	
Styryl	—	—	—	

FIG. 1

FIG. 1 (cont.)

EXPERIMENTAL

(The m.p.s are uncorrected. The absorptions were recorded on a Beckmann DU Model spectrophotometer. The sensitisations were recorded on an Adam Hilger Wedge Spectrograph using a 150 c.p. point-o-lite A.C. lamp as a light source. Ilford N 40 process plates were used. The plates were dipped in dye solutions (1/100,000 in 30% rectified spirit) for 5 minutes, drained and dried. Exposure: 4 minutes.

1-Diethylamino-4-naphthaldehyde (1). Diethyl- α -naphthylamine (40 g), hexamine (40 g), rectified spirit (40 ml) and 40 ml of mixed acids (out of a mixture of 60 ml acetic acid and 60 ml 90% formic acid) were refluxed on steam bath. The remaining mixed acid was added in six instalments at 30 min. intervals. The mixture was refluxed for a total period of 6 hr. and then poured with stirring into 600 ml of .5 N HCl and left overnight. The aldehyde which separated as a thick yellow oil was taken up in ether, the ether extract washed and dried over anhydrous $MgSO_4$. After the evaporation of ether, the thick yellow liquid was distilled under reduced pressure and the distillate, b.p. 170° - 200° , 5 mm. (5.5 g, 13.75%) was collected. *Semicarbazone*: faint yellow wooly crystals, m.p. 196° - 197° . *DNP*: chocolate brown crystals, m.p. 208° (Found: C, 61.2; H, 5.02; N, 17.45. $C_{21}H_{21}N_5O_4$ requires: C, 61.9; H, 5.16; N, 17.2%).

Oxidation of the Aldehyde (1). (a) 1 g. of the aldehyde was oxidised by boiling with excess of acidified potassium permanganate solution for 15 min. It was then filtered hot and the filtrate on cooling gave 0.3 g of phthalic acid, m.p. 195° (d). This on warming with a little conc. H_2SO_4 and resorcinol gave a green fluorescence.

(b) To a vigorously agitated mixture of 5g. of the aldehyde and 130 ml of water, 6 ml conc. sulphuric acid was slowly added. The aldehyde dissolved. The solution was

boiled and rapidly poured into a mixture of 4.5 g. potassium dichromate in 65 ml water. The mixture was then filtered hot and the filtrate steam distilled. The distillate was ether extracted and on concentration long yellow needles of α -naphthoquinone separated. Yield 0.8 g, m.p. 124°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic sample gave no depression.

2-(4'-Diethylamino-1'-naphthylidene)-6-chlorobenzthiazole Methiodide (IIa). 2-Methyl-6-chlorobenzthiazole methiodide (0.976 g) and 4-diethylamino-1-naphthaldehyde (0.681 g) were refluxed for 2 hr. in absolute ethanol (50 ml) with pyridine (4 drops). The dye began to separate while refluxing. On cooling, 0.86 g. (53 %) of the dye was obtained. It was recrystallised from methanol as lustrous deep green needles, m.p. 227°. (Found: C, 53.65; H, 4.45; N, 5.24. $C_{24}H_{24}N_2S$ requires: C, 53.88; H, 4.49; N, 5.23%).

2-(4'-Diethylamino-1'-naphthylidene)-6-bromoquinoline Methiodide (IIb). 6-Bromoquinoline methiodide (0.72 g.) and 4-diethylamino-1-naphthaldehyde (0.45 g) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) with pyridine (4 drops) were refluxed for 2 hr. A small quantity of dye separated while under reflux. On cooling 0.44 g (38.4 %) of the dye was obtained. It was recrystallised from methanol as a black powdery solid, m.p. 207° (Found: C, 54.4; H, 4.54; N, 4.73. $C_{26}H_{26}N_2Br$ requires: C, 54.45; H, 4.54; N, 4.88%).

2-(4'-Diethylamino-1'-naphthylidene)-4-methylthiazole Methiodide (IIc). 2:4-Dimethylthiazole methiodide (0.26 g) and 4-diethylamino-1-naphthaldehyde (0.23 g) in 10 ml pyridine were refluxed for 4 hr. On concentration to about 3 ml, 0.23 g (47%) of the dye was deposited. It was recrystallised from ethanol as shining maroon needles, m.p. 202°. (Found: C, 54.0; H, 5.1; N, 5.89. $C_{21}H_{25}N_2S$ requires: C, 54.3; H, 5.3; N, 6.03%).

2-(ω -*p*-Dimethylaminophenyl-butadienyl)-4-methylthiazole Methiodide (IIIa). 2:4-Dimethylthiazole methiodide (0.5 g) and *p*-dimethylaminocinnamic aldehyde (0.35 g) in absolute ethanol (10 ml) with piperidine (2 drops) were refluxed for 30 min. On cooling 0.38 g (46%) of the dye separated. It was recrystallised from ethanol as blue shining crystals, m.p. 253°(d). (Found: C, 47.7; H, 5.06; N, 6.89. $C_{16}H_{21}N_2S$ requires: C, 48.0; H, 5.25; N, 7.0%).

2-(ω -*p*-Dimethylaminophenyl-butadienyl)-4-methylbenzthiazole Methiodide (IIIb). 2:4-Dimethylbenzthiazole methiodide (0.3 g) and *p*-dimethylaminocinnamic aldehyde (0.17 g) in absolute ethanol (10 ml) with 2 drops of piperidine were refluxed for 1 hr. On cooling, the dye (0.1 g., 22%) separated. It was recrystallised from ethanol as fine black crystals, m.p. 188°. (Found: C, 54.3; H, 4.90; N, 5.9. $C_{21}H_{23}N_2S$ requires: C, 54.5; H, 4.97; N, 6.06%).

2-*p*-Dimethylamino- β -methylstyryl-5-methylbenzthiazole Methiodide (IV): 2:5-Dimethylbenzthiazole methiodide (0.6 g) and *p*-dimethylaminoacetophenone (6.24 g) in acetic anhydride (15 ml) were refluxed for 2 hr. The dye (0.05 g; 7.4%) which separated on cooling was recrystallised from methanol as a dark powder, m.p. 234°. (Found: C, 53.12; H, 5.08; N, 6.18. $C_{20}H_{23}N_2S$ requires: C, 53.3; H, 5.11; N, 6.22%).

2-(β -Methyl- ω -*p*-dimethylaminophenyl-butadienyl)-6-methylbenzthiazole Methiodide (V). 2:6-Dimethylbenzthiazole methiodide (0.46 g), *p*-dimethylaminostyryl methyl ketone (0.28 g), absolute ethanol (10 ml) and 2 drops piperidine were refluxed for 3 hr. On cooling, the dye (0.2 g, 28.2%) separated and was recrystallised from methanol as scarlet shining needles, m.p. 263°. (Found: C, 55.2; H, 5.1; N, 5.73. $C_{22}H_{25}N_2S$ requires: C, 55.4, H, 5.25; N, 5.88%).

Thanks are due to Dr. G. Jacob, Ex-Vice-Chancellor, Patna University for a personal research grant to one of us (J.C.B.), to Professor S. P. Ghosh, for the loan of an Adam Hilger Wedge Spectrograph and to Professor J. N. Chatterjea, for the absorption data, analysis and for numerous valuable suggestions.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
B. N. COLLEGE, PATNA 4.
AND
CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
RAJENDRA COLLEGE, CHAPRA.

Received, June 12, 1965.